

stems exceeded 40%. Two crop loss assessment experiments indicated that substantial yield loss is caused by larval feeding.

To control yellow rice borer, half of a farmer's field received 22 insecticide applications (2 basal applications of carbofuran and 20 sprays of diazinon). The other half served as a check. Grain yields and borer incidence at harvest were assessed in 5 paired plots 16 m² each. Yellow rice borer was the predominant pest species. Despite the intensive insecticide schedule, 9% of the stems in the treated plot were infested and whiteheads were present (see table). The high level of borer activity in the untreated plot was associated with a 21.0% reduction in yield. Correcting for the infested stems in the treated plot gave a 31% total yield loss.

Yellow rice borer incidence at harvest and grain yields in a farmer's field at Agrakhola and in a pot experiment at Joydebpur, Bangladesh, 1978.

Treatment	Infested stems (%)	Whiteheads (no./16 m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Grain wt (g/pot)	Panicle wt (g)
<i>Farmer's field, Agrakhola</i>					
Insecticide-treated	9.0	14.4	3.8		
Check	33.2	31.2	3.0		
Difference	24.2**	22.8**	0.8**		
<i>Pot experiment, Joydebpur</i>					
Pots exposed to borers	21.5	—	—	16.6	1.6
Pots not exposed to borers	1.5	—	—	26.2	2.2
Difference	20.0**	—	—	9.6**	0.6**

At Joydebpur, two matched sets of potted Habiganj Aman II plants were allowed to elongate in metal tanks. One set was then exposed to yellow rice borers. Larval feeding reduced grain weight by 36.7%. Yield loss was due mainly to a reduction (27.7%) in panicle

weight and, to a lesser extent, to a reduction in panicle number (13.2%). As a result of larval feeding, plants exposed to borers had fewer main stems and basal tillers but compensated for the damage by producing more branches (nodal tillers). ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Reaction of rice varieties to heat injury

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Seventy-three IRR1 rice cultivars were sown in raised nursery beds on 2 June 1979 at Borkhera. Germination was good and uniform. When seedlings were 9 days old, the maximum daily temperature rose suddenly and ranged from 45.6 to 47.2°C during a 1 week period.

The degree of seedling mortality due to heat injury varied considerably. The varieties with less than 30% seedling mortality were rated as resistant; those

with 31 to 60% mortality were moderately susceptible; and those with more than 60% highly susceptible. The rices were classified according to seedling mortality as follows:

- *Resistant*: Getu, CSR 1, CSR 3, IET5233, IR2053-436-1-2, IR2307-247-2-2-3, IR4227-104-3-3-1, IR4227-109-1-3-3, IR4422-480-2-3-1, IR4573-22-3-17, IR4707-34-3-1, IR4711-34-2-3, IR34816-70-1, IR4819-77-1-2, IR4859-38-3-3, IR5623-97-3, IR5623-189-3, Pokkali, MR359, Nona Bokra, Nona Sail, C23-2-1, C23-51, IR4-11, IR4639-57-3-1, IR153-9430-3, IR26, IR4432-28-5, IR4595-4-1-15, IR4619-48-3-3-6-1, IR4630-22-2-5-1-2,

IR4763-73-1-12, IR9884-3-3, IR9884-54-3, IR10168-52-4-2, IR10198-66-2, IR330206-18-3, IR330206-29-2, K19-1, KI14-1, Pattambi 25315, Pattambi 25316, Pattambi 25331, Pattambi 25333, Pattambi 25335, Pattambi 25336, Pattambi 25337, TNAU17069, TNAU13223-7-2, H33, M23, M114, M117, M152, M242, and M432.

- *Moderately susceptible*: IR4829-89-2-1, IR5785-37-1, IR35785-162-3, IR5853-118-5, IR11418-15-2, Lemo, IR42, IR1820-210-2, and TNAU 17005.

- *Susceptible*: Palman 579, IR4870-15-1-1, IR9109-71-2-1, IR11418-19-2-3, and M148. ■

Pest management and control

Search for alternate insect vectors of rice ragged stunt disease

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The ability of *Nephotettix nigropictus*,

N. virescens, *Recilia dorsalis*, and *Sogatella furcifera* to transmit rice ragged stunt was tested through daily serial transmission with different acquisition access times.

A total of 14,443 seedlings of TN1 were inoculated by 1,182 insects (542

seedlings by 98 *N. nigropictus* with 2- or 4-day acquisition feeding, 2,290 seedlings by 120 *N. virescens* with 4-day acquisition feeding, 8,546 seedlings by 785 *R. dorsalis* with 1- to 16-day acquisition feeding, and 3,065 seedlings by 179 *S. furcifera* with 2- or 4-day

acquisition feeding). None of the inoculated seedlings showed symptoms of rice ragged stunt disease. Consequently these species of insects may not be vectors of rice ragged stunt. ■

Occurrence of tungro disease in Nepal

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Rice plants with symptoms characteristic of tungro were observed in the early to mid-tillering stages at the Rice Research Station, Parwanipur, in Nepal's tarai region. The plants were stunted; some leaves, particularly the outer ones toward the tips, were bright orange-yellow. A casual examination of vectors clearly showed the predominance in the area of *Nephotettix virescens*, the most efficient tungro vector.

Insects fed on suspected material were taken to the greenhouse at Khumaltar and inoculated under protected conditions to Taichung 176 seedlings at the 3- to 4-leaf stage. Thirty percent of the seedlings reacted positively within 10 days; their symptoms were similar to those described earlier. Parwanipur is near Bihar, India, where tungro occurs. More work is under way to further characterize the virus disease. ■

Interaction of sugars on the sporulation of *Drechslera oryzae*

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Preliminary studies have indicated that mannose, starch, and sucrose enhance *D. oryzae* sporulation in Richards medium. Sporulation was not increased by arabinose, carboxycellulose, fructose, galactose, glucose, rhamnose, ribose, or xylose. Because glucose is abundant in fresh rice tissue, further experiments were conducted to compare glucose with other sugars.

The glucose concentration was varied

from 0.4 to 3.2% in a basal medium containing 2.5%, of sucrose, 2.5%, of mannose, and 6.5% starch. Those concentrations maximized sporulation, so they were used in the study.

Glucose at 0.4% suppressed sporulation completely in media containing 2.5% sucrose and 2.5% mannose. In a medium with 6.5% starch, 0.4% glucose failed to completely suppress sporulation but sporulation was reduced with increased glucose concentration (see table). Concentrations of more than 0.8% completely suppressed sporulation.

The effects of cellulose, glucose, and starch on sporulation were further tested, both individually and in combination because those sugars are abundant in the rice plant. Concentrations of those sugars were standardized by using maximum

mycelial growth or sporulation observed in preliminary experiments.

Sporulation was observed only in starch and in the carboxycellulose + starch combination. Sporulation was highest in the carboxycellulose + starch combination. ■

Effect of different carbon sources on sporulation of *D. oryzae*. Karnataka, India.

Carbon source and concentration	Spores (%)
Carboxycellulose (3.5%)	<i>a</i>
Glucose (0.8%)	<i>a</i>
Starch (6.5%)	88.50 x 10 ⁴
Carboxycellulose (3.5%) + glucose (0.8%)	<i>a</i>
Carboxycellulose (3.5%) + starch (6.5%)	102.50 x 10 ⁴
Glucose (0.8%) + starch (6.5%)	<i>a</i>
Carboxycellulose (3.5%) + glucose (0.8%) + starch (6.5%)	<i>a</i>

a = no sporulation.

Leaf blast control by seed treatment with systemic fungicides

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Leaf blast, caused by *Pyricularia oryzae*, is often a serious disease in seedbeds and may severely damage dryland rice at the seedling stage. Several experiments were conducted to determine the

effectiveness of systemic fungicides as seed treatments in *P. oryzae* control. Seeds of the blast-susceptible line IR442-2-58 were treated with powder formulations of the fungicides and then either planted in soil in plastic trays and placed in blast nursery beds, or seeded directly into blast nursery beds. The seedlings were continuously exposed to *P. oryzae* spores produced on inoculated border rows of IR442-2-58. Two weeks after seeding, the plants

Effect of seed treatment with systemic fungicides on leaf blast control in rice variety IR442-2-58 at 3-6 weeks after seeding.

Treatment		Lesions ^a (mean no./seedling)			
Fungicide	Rate (g/kg seed)	3 wk	4 wk	5 wk	6 wk
CGA49104 50 WP	4	0.015	7.7	13.6	23.5
	8	0.05	2.3	5.5	8.9
	16	0.0	1.9	1.9	—
	32	0.0	0.0	0.0	—
	40	0.0	0.0	0.9	—
PP389 50 WP	16	0.0	47.1	57.6	—
	20	15.3	41.9	57.6	79.2
	32	0.2	19.4	19.6	—
	40	0.7	5.0	9.1	8.8
Thiophanate methyl	20	40.0	106.0	138.4	158.8
	40	17.5	57.7	71.0	120.5
Benomyl 50 WP	20	52.0	129.8	166.6	188.4
	40	22.6	100.5	145.3	159.0
Untreated	0	53.7	165.0	196.1	234.7

^a — means no data (experiment was terminated).